

Mercuration of Compounds Containing the Reactive Methylene Group.

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The mercuration of the substituted amides of malonic acid was undertaken with a view to study the change in the stability of the carbon-mercury linkage in these compounds and thus throw, if possible, some light on the effect of the adjoining groups on the reactivity of the two hydrogen atoms of a methylene group situated between two negative groups, which has been the subject of investigation by Naik and his collaborators (Naik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 879 and subsequent papers).

We have employed the method of Neogi and Chatterjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 221), the mercurating agent being mercuric chloride in presence of sodium bicarbonate and glycerol. It may be that at first an oxychloride of mercury is formed, which subsequently reacts with the organic compounds giving rise to a mercurated product, thus:—

The following compounds were mercurated by this method:—(1) Malonamide, (2) malondimethylamide, (3) malondiethylamide, (4) malondipropylamide, (5) malondi-*n*-butylamide, (6) malondi*isobutyl*-amide, (7) malondi*isopentyl*amide, (8) malondiamylamide, (9) malon-diheptylamide, and (10) ethyl malonate.

Of these (7) and (8) were prepared for the first time. Only the alkylamides of malonic acid were selected for the present purpose, in order to avoid the complications that may occur by the entrance of mercury in the nuclei of arylamides.

All the substances enumerated above react with mercuric chloride under the experimental conditions yielding products having the general formula,

where R = ethoxy-, amino-, methylamino-, etc. group.

This constitution has been assigned to the compounds from the following considerations—

(i) The mercury has not entered the aliphatic part of the amido-group (—NHR) because—

(a) no example seems to have been recorded in literature of mercury having thus substituted a hydrogen atom of an aliphatic compounds ;

(b) malonamide, which contains no such aliphatic part, forms a similar mercury derivative ;

(c) the mercury derivatives of aliphatic compounds are not easily decomposed by potassium iodide and hydrochloric acid, while dichloromercurimalondiheptylamide, obtained during the course of this work, is attacked by these reagents giving the original amide.

(ii) The mercury atom has not replaced the *N*-hydrogen atom, for

(a) malonic ester which contains no such hydrogen atom forms a similar compound with mercuric chloride ;

(b) a study of the known mercurated *substituted* amides shows that the hydrogen attached to nitrogen can be substituted by mercury under exceptional conditions. Acetanilide on fusion with mercuric oxide forms *N*-mercuri-bis-acetanilide (Oppenheim and Paëff, *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 624 ; Wheeler, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1896, 18, 696 ; Pesci, *Gazzetta*, 1897, I, 27, 568), though a boiling solution of acetanilide gives *p*-acetaminophenylmercuric acetate (Pesci, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1897, 15, 222 ; Dimroth, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2037). Similarly *p*-acetoxymmercuri-*o*-acetotoluidide is formed by refluxing *o*-acetotoluidide with mercuric acetate in water (Schrauth, Schoeller and Rother, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 2812) while no *N*-mercury-derivative of the same seems to have been reported. Similar results are obtained with *m*- and *p*-acetotoluidides ;

(c) the *N*-Hg-compounds behave as weak bases and a solution of mercuri-acetamide can be titrated with hydrochloric acid using methyl orange as indicator (Ley and Kissel, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1357), while the products obtained here are decomposed rather slowly.

(iii) The mercury is directly attached to the methylene carbon atom, for—

(a) dichloromercurimalonamide gives dibromomalonamide on treatment with bromine ;

(b) the properties and behaviour of the products obtained is the same as those of compounds having mercury attached to the carbon in α -position to a keto-group, as is shown below.

The stability of the carbon-mercury bond varies over a very wide range. Thus, in contrast to some of the mercarbides which remain unchanged even after prolonged boiling with fuming hydrochloric acid (Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 1905 ; 1900, 33, 1886), substances having a mercury atom attached to a carbon atom in α -position to a keto-group, lose it on treatment with 0.25N-hydrochloric acid (Dimroth, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2870).

Ethyl dichloromercurimalonate $(\text{HgCl})_2 : \text{C} : (\text{CO}_2\text{Et})_2$, which was also prepared by Biilmann (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2580), on treatment with hot concentrated hydrochloric acid, liberates mercuric chloride and forms ethyl monochloromercurimalonate, thus :

It is rather curious to observe that the second mercury atom in the same position is not removed simultaneously. This behaviour is not, however, quite abnormal, for bromomercuriacetic acid, $\text{BrHg} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO}_2\text{H}$, which contains a mercury atom attached to a carbon atom in α -position to a keto group, is not decomposed by acids (Hofmann and Sand, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 1346). In the case of dichloromercurimalondiheptylamide, on the other hand, both the chloromercuri-groups are removed by the action of hydrochloric acid.

It has also been possible to obtain ethyl monochloromercurimalonate by the action of *cold* aqueous potassium iodide on the dichloromercuri-ester, though both the chloromercuri-groups are removed by the action of *hot* potassium iodide solution. Potassium iodide reacts with organo-mercury compounds of the type $\text{R} \cdot \text{HgX}$ in three different ways: (i) it may give rise to compounds of the type $\text{R} \cdot \text{HgI}$ (Whitmore, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 1850); (ii) it may form an iodomercuri-compound, $\text{R} \cdot \text{HgI}$ (Volhard, *Annalen*, 1892, 267, 172), or (iii) it may bring about a complete splitting up of the carbon-mercury linkage with the liberation of one equivalent of alkali for each carbon-mercury linkage, thus :

All compounds having mercury substituted for the hydrogen atoms in the grouping, $-\text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO}-$, $-\text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CN}$, etc., behave in the above manner (Biilmann, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2580 ; Biil-

mann and Witt, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 1070 ; Petterson, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1912, *ii*, **86**, 464). Dichloromercurimalondiheptylamide is also decomposed by potassium iodide, with the liberation of two equivalents of alkali.

The substances containing mercury in the reactive methylene group are unusually reactive towards hydrogen sulphide, immediately giving mercuric sulphide (Billmann, *loc. cit.* ; Billmann and Witt, *loc. cit.* ; Lippmann, *Z. Chem.*, 1869, *ii*, **5**, 29 ; Oppenheim, *Ber.*, 1877, **10**, 701 ; Behrend, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1893, **11**, 478 ; Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 2215 ; Ley, *Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 1014 ; Michael, *Ber.*, 1905, **38**, 2090) ; ethyl dichloromercurimalonate instantaneously gives a black precipitate of mercuric sulphide on treatment with hydrogen sulphide.

Sodium thiosulphate is the most general reagent used to bring about a change from the organo-mercury compounds of the type $R \cdot HgX$ to compounds of the type $R_2 : Hg$ (Pesci, *Gazzetta*, 1899, **I**, **29**, 394 ; Dimroth, *Ber.*, 1908, **35**, 2041 ; Kharasch and Piccard, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1861 ; Whitmore and Middleton, *ibid.*, 1921, **43**, 622, etc.). However, when ethyl dichloromercurimalonate was dissolved in concentrated sodium thiosulphate solution, only a negligible amount of a red substance was deposited after standing for a day.

Freund (*Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 133) obtained a compound from malonamide and mercuric oxide to which he assigned the formula $CH_2 : (CONH)_2 : Hg$, because dibromomalonamide also gives a similar compound, $CBr_2 : (CONH)_2 : Hg$ (Freund, *Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 785). However for the aforesaid reasons, dichloromercurimalonamide has been assigned the formula $(ClHg)_2 : C : (CONH_2)_2$.

It has been observed by Naik and his co-workers that in a series like—

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|--|---|
| (i) $CH_2(CO \cdot NH_2)_2$ | (iv) $RNH \cdot CO \cdot CH_2 \cdot CO_2Et$ |
| (ii) $RNH \cdot CO \cdot CH_2 \cdot CO \cdot NH_2$ | (v) $CN \cdot CH_2 \cdot CO_2Et$ |
| (iii) $CH_2(CO \cdot NHR)_2$ | (vi) $CH_2(CO_2Et)_2$ |

the reactivity of the methylene hydrogen atoms increases from (i) to (vi). If it be assumed that the chloromercuri-group which replaces a hydrogen atom of the methylene group is attached to the carbon atom with the same degree of tenacity as the corresponding hydrogen atoms, then the decomposition of the chloromercuri-derivatives

of such compounds by potassium iodide, etc., will also be in the order of this reactivity. This has actually been found to be the case, for dichloromercurimalondiheptylamide reacts with potassium iodide more slowly than does ethyl dichloromercurimalonate.

Mercury in these compounds was estimated by the Francois' method; while chlorine was estimated by the Carius' method, but the precipitate of silver chloride was filtered and washed in the cold, on account of the solubility of silver chloride in hot water in the presence of mercuric salts.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl Dichloromercurimalonate.—Ethyl malonate (2 g.) and mercuric chloride (7 g.) were dissolved in dilute (30%) alcohol and glycerol (20 c.c.) added. A solution of sodium bicarbonate (2.5 g.) was slowly added to it with constant stirring. After some time small silky needles began to come down. These were filtered after two hours and repeatedly washed with dilute alcohol. The substance is insoluble in any of the ordinary solvents. It does not melt below 300°. (Found: Hg, 64.10; Cl, 11.14. $C_7H_{10}O_4Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 68.59; Cl, 11.28 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on the above.—The substance (1 g.) was suspended in dilute alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) added. After refluxing for half an hour, the residue was filtered and washed. The filtrate was found to contain mercuric chloride. The substance was insoluble in any solvent and does not melt but turns grey at 192.5°. (Found: Hg, 50.93; Cl, 8.52. $C_7H_{11}O_4ClHg$ requires Hg, 50.69; Cl, 8.92 per cent.)

Action of Hydrogen Sulphide.—When hydrogen sulphide was slowly passed into a hot alcoholic suspension of the substance, a black precipitate of mercuric sulphide was obtained.

Action of Sodium Thiosulphate.—The substance completely went into solution in a 50% solution of sodium thiosulphate. On standing for twenty-four hours, a very small amount of a red substance was deposited.

Action of Potassium Iodide.—(a) *Alcoholic*. The compound (0.2036 g.) was suspended in alcohol and potassium iodide (2 g.) added. After half an hour, the alkali liberated, required 3.4 c.c. of 0.098N hydrochloric acid. It was then refluxed for four hours on a

water-bath, when a further amount of alkali equivalent to 3.2 c.c. of 0.098N hydrochloric acid was liberated.

	Calc.	Found.
Equivalent of alkali. ...	1	1.03
	2	1.99

(b) *Aqueous*. The substance was shaken for half an hour with an aqueous solution of potassium iodide, and the residue was filtered and washed with alcohol. On analysis it was found to be identical with ethyl monochloromercurimalonate. (Found : Hg, 51.15 ; Cl, 9.23 per cent).

Dichloromercurimalonamide.—Malonamide (2 g.) and mercuric chloride (11 g.) were dissolved in water, and glycerol (20 c.c.) was added. An aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate (4 g.) was then added to it. After an hour the whole liquid became slightly yellowish. The yellow floating particles coagulated and were easily filtered. The filtrate that came down was a milky solution containing the product in colloidal suspension. It was, therefore, allowed to stand for five days, when the colloidal mass came down in small cubic crystals. This was filtered and repeatedly washed with water.

It is soluble in alcohol, benzene and ether; the pure substance shrinks at 191.2° and melts with decomposition at 220°. (Found : Hg, 70.5 ; Cl, 12.32. $C_3H_4O_2N_2Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 70.05 ; Cl, 12.43 per cent.)

Action of Bromine on the above.—Aqueous bromine was slowly added to a suspension of the compound in water, till it was no longer absorbed. The residue was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol ; m.p. 203°. It is identical with dibromomalonamide.

Dichloromercurimalondimethylamide.—It was prepared by a similar process. It is soluble in chloroform, benzene, methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol, and melts at 241° (decomp). (Found : Hg, 66.6 ; Cl, 11.90. $C_5H_8O_2N_2Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 66.77 ; Cl, 11.85 per cent.)

Dichloromercurimalondiethylamide.—This was prepared by the same method, but in dilute alcoholic solution. It crystallised after three days in cubic crystals. It is soluble in ether, benzene, chloroform and alcohol and has no definite melting point but decomposes turning yellow at 191°. (Found : Hg, 63.5 ; Cl, 11.65. $C_7H_{12}O_2N_2Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 63.79 ; Cl, 11.32 per cent.)

Dichloromercurimalondipropylamide.—This was similarly prepared. The product was separated on the next day. It does not crystallise like the foregoing members if allowed to remain longer in contact with the solution, but instead gelatinises, which can neither be filtered nor separated. It is soluble in alcohol, ether, chloroform and benzene; it changes colour at 162° and melts at 173.5°. (Found: Hg, 61.5; Cl, 10.72. $C_9H_{16}O_2N_2Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 61.06; Cl, 10.84 per cent.)

Dichloromercurimalondibutylamide.—Prepared in the same way as above, it was washed with dilute alcohol, as it has a tendency to gelatinise in presence of ordinary solvents. This property is also shared by the following products. It is soluble in alcohol, ether, and benzene; m.p. 90°. (Found: Hg, 58.4; Cl, 9.95. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_2Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 58.56; Cl, 10.39 per cent.)

Dichloromercurimalondiisobutylamide.—It was separated on the next day. It is soluble in alcohol, ether, benzene and chloroform; m.p. 108.9°. (Found: Hg, 58.8; Cl, 10.52. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_2Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 58.56; Cl, 10.39 per cent.)

Preparation of Malondiamylamide.—This was prepared by the same method as used by Backes, West and Whiteley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 359) for the preparation of alkylmalonamides. Ethyl malonate (8 g.) and amylamine (8.7 g.) were mixed up in a sealed tube and allowed to remain at ordinary temperature for 24 hours, and then heated at 120°, for six hours. After cooling, the solid was washed out with petroleum and recrystallised from benzene m.p. 126° (yield, 80 %). It is very soluble in benzene, alcohol, ether, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride but slightly so in petroleum. (Found: N, 12.0. $C_{13}H_{26}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.57 per cent.)

Dichloromercurimalondiamylamide.—The product became quite granular within three hours and could therefore be separated. It was converted into a gelatinous product even on standing for a day. It melts with decomposition at 143°. (Found: Hg, 56.5; Cl, 9.94. $C_{13}H_{24}O_2N_2Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 56.25; Cl, 9.98 per cent.)

Malondiisoamylamide.—Amylamine (9 g.) and ethyl malonate (8 g.) were mixed up in a sealed tube and allowed to remain for a day. This was, afterwards, heated for 12 hours at 200°. The contents were taken out and concentrated on a water-bath, when a thick syrupy liquid was obtained. This was allowed to remain at ordinary temperature for three days, when long needles separated.

These were separated by washing with the least amount of petroleum and recrystallised from benzene (yield, 20%).

It is very soluble in alcohol, benzene, chloroform, ether and acetic acid, but less so in petroleum and water; m.p. 55°. (Found : N, 12.1. $C_{13}H_{26}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.57 per cent.)

Dichloromercurimalondiisocamylamide.—It was prepared from malondiisocamylamide. It is soluble in alcohol, benzene, chloroform and ether; m.p. 105°. (Found : Hg, 56.3; Cl, 9.85. $C_{13}H_{24}O_2N_2Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 56.25; Cl, 9.98 per cent.)

Dichloromercurimalondiheptylamide.—This was prepared like the other compounds and separated after two hours; m.p. 117°. (Found : Hg, 52.4; Cl, 9.50. $C_{17}H_{32}O_2N_2Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 52.15; Cl, 9.25 per cent.)

Action of Alcoholic Potassium Iodide on the Above.—The dry substance (0.1890 g.) was suspended in alcohol and an alcoholic solution of potassium iodide (2 g.) was added. Even after two days an amount of alkali equivalent to 1.5 c.c. of 0.098N-hydrochloric acid was liberated. It was then refluxed for six hours, when the total amount of alkali liberated was found to be equivalent to 5 c.c. of 0.098N-hydrochloric acid.

	Calc.	Found.
Equivalent of alkali	... 2	1.97

Action of Hydrochloric Acid.—The substance (0.5 g.) was suspended in water and 1 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added. On heating for fifteen minutes a white substance was obtained which was crystallised from alcohol and found to be identical with malondiheptylamide.

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